

PENSION FUND INVESTMENT STRATEGIES AND PENSION FUND SUSTAINABILITY IN NIGERIA.

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15824229>

ABSTRACT

This study examined the pension fund investment strategies and pension fund sustainability using primary data obtained from active and retired staff of the University of Teaching Hospital (UBTH), Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. The objective was to ascertain the perception of pension fund investment strategies from the beneficiaries' perspective. Across-sectional research design was adopted, and 4668 active and retired staff from 2010 to 2022 of the UBTH who benefited from the contributory pension scheme, irrespective of their positions, constituted the research population. The sample size used for the study was 400 respondents. The questionnaire was administered as the research instrument for data collection. Data analysis engaged descriptive statistics and linear regression analysis to test the hypothesis of the study at 5% significance level. The study found that pension fund sustainability is significant and positively related to pension fund investment strategies. The study recommends continued adherence to investment guidelines issued by the National Pension Commission as a way of ensuring the sustainability of the contributory pension scheme in Nigeria.

KEY WORDS: Pension Sustainability, Pension Fund Investment Strategies, Pension Fund Administrators, National Pension Commission, Contributory Pension Scheme.

Introduction

The commencement of the contributory pension scheme in Nigeria signaled new dimensions in pension administration in the country. A major input is the evolution of pension fund investment in categories of portfolios as stipulated by the National Pension Commission's (PenCom) guideline through the Pension Fund Custodians and the Pension Fund Administrators. Pension assets and investments since their inception in 2004 have grown steadily. In the year 2024, the pension industry netted a 23 per cent growth with a pension fund of ₦22.5 trillion (Adebayo, 2025). This huge fund would need to be strategically managed, especially because it is a fund from which returns are expected.

As a proactive step towards managing the pension fund, Section 85 of the Pension Reform Act (2014) stipulates that pension contributions should be invested by the pension fund administrators into specific investment outlays to ensure the security of the pension fund and the maintenance of reasonable returns on the amount invested. This was further buttressed by Section 86 of the enabling Act, with a breakdown of the nature of investments that should be permitted and approved by the National Pension Commission for pension fund speculations, which are:

“bonds, bills and other securities issued or guaranteed by the Federal Government and the Central Bank of Nigeria; bonds, debentures, redeemable preference shares and other debt instruments issued by corporate entities and listed on a Stock Exchange registered under the Investments and Securities Act, 1999; ordinary shares of public limited companies listed on a Stock Exchange registered under the Investments and Securities Act 1999; with good track records having

declared and paid dividends in the preceding five years; bank deposits and bank securities; investment certificates of closed-end investment funds or hybrid investment funds listed on a Stock Exchange registered under the Investments and Securities Act, 1999 with a good track record of earning; units sold by open-end investment funds or specialist open-end investment funds listed on the Stock Exchange recognised by the Commission; bonds and other debt securities issued by listed companies; real estate investment; and such other instruments as the Commission may, from time to time, prescribe.”

Furthermore, Section 87 of the Pension Reform Act (2014) specifies the opportunity for pension funds to be invested in other countries by the pension fund administrators, provided that such investments are expended in the classes of investments set out above and real estate property. However, this investment type shall be subject to the standing foreign exchange rules of the Central Bank of Nigeria and the endorsement of the President through the National Pension Commission.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the laudable provisions of the Act, the investment categories and the stringent conditions required for pension fund speculations, several studies have emerged raising concerns about pension fund sustainability with the aforementioned type of portfolios. Adekunle et al.'s (2019) study has noted that the pension fund investment strategies do not have a substantial positive or negative influence on fund sustainability. The study further observed that beneficiaries of the contributory pension scheme in Lagos State perceive the investment strategies as inadequate, inconsiderate and unreasonable. This position was corroborated by (Olanrewaju et al., 2023;

Didal et al., 2023; Oloruntoba & Jimoh, 2021; Ikwue et al., 2023). These studies raised issues of transparency, compliance and impact of inflation on pension fund investment and management and concluded that Nigeria is standing at a crossroads in terms of nurturing a culture of a sustainable pension fund.

The paradox of crossroads in pension fund investments calls for the re-examination of pension fund investment strategies and pension fund sustainability in Nigeria. Although the National Pension Commission's annual reports have consistently shown a positive outlook of pension fund investment portfolios, which by implication suggests the sustainability of the pension fund, it is not known if the beneficiaries share the same perspective. There is a need to further evaluate the opinion of beneficiaries outside Lagos state to create a robust literature on the subject matter. It is in this light that the study examined pension fund investment strategies through the perspective of the beneficiaries in the University of Benin Teaching Hospital using both retired and active staff of the organisation.

Research Objectives/Question

The objective of this study was to ascertain with the aid of empirical evidence whether the pension fund investment strategies introduced into the Nigerian pension administration by the Act are contributing to its sustenance. The fundamental question underlying the study is: What is the nature of the relationship between pension fund investment strategies and pension fund sustainability in Nigeria? If it is significant, what is the level of significance?

Research Hypothesis

The hypothesis used to guide the study is stated in the null form below:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between pension fund investment strategies and pension fund sustainability.

Review of Literature

Sustainability as a construct is traceable to the 1987 United Nations Report facilitated by the Brundtland Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development, tagged “Our Common Future.” Though the report primarily focused on environmental sustainability, it has become a useful tool in management. Mollenkamp (2022) described sustainability as the capacity to preserve or support a practice uninterruptedly over time. Ozili (2022) saw sustainability as a “philosophical approach that efficiently guides today to ensure that resources are available and sufficient to meet today’s needs and the needs of future generations”. He further noted that sustainability has to do with the capacity to make responsible decisions in the use and allocation of resources for economic and non-economic activities to achieve desired social, economic and environmental ends. Therefore, it can be asserted that pension fund sustainability refers to a pension scheme that can meet the needs and obligations of its stakeholders financially, socially and otherwise now and in the future.

Investment, on the other hand, has been described as the sacrifice of today’s resources in anticipation of earning more resources in the future (Laopodis, 2020). In Ijeoma and Nwufu (2015), it was posited that with a sound investment strategy and risk management system, there is a guarantee for the contributory pension scheme in Nigeria. Okparaka and Makwe (2019) established that investment in the pension industry has no significant influence over financial depth and liquidity intermediation in Nigeria. Nwawolo and Nwogwugwu's (2019) study discovered that pension contributors’ opinion of pension deposit investment demonstrated positive and significant influence on pensioners’ living standard. Afolabia and Erasmus (2023)

observed that the greater the administrative overheads, the greater the pension entitlement paid to beneficiaries. They asserted that a rise in operational overheads stimulates greater contribution inflows investment in government bonds, especially treasury bills, which stimulates greater investment proceeds. Ogonda and Okiakpe (2022) advocated that investment of pension assets should be allocated more to corporate securities and ordinary shares, while pension fund investment in money market securities should not be encouraged, and that of the federal government securities should be done with care if the contributory pension is to be sustained. Obasa (2023) asserted that a nation's ability to sustain the contributory pension system is dependent on the investment strategy implemented by its enabling pension act. The higher the returns on the investment portfolios, the likelihood the security of the pension fund, the higher the retiree's benefit upon retirement. The study added that the impact assessment of the contributory pension scheme investment strategies on prospective pensioner's pension fund in Nigeria indicates a pension management that is huge in investment generation. Manor (2019) called for a life cycle dynamics of pension strategies with greater share of equities, moving progressively to bonds portfolio upon retirement as a means of ensuring pension fund sustainability. Bocchialinia, et al. (2025) emphasized that a sustainable driver of pension plans is the incorporation of Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) choices in financial portfolios as it significantly correlates with pension plans sustainability of investment choices. Wanger, et al. (2024) observed that though pension funds investment is diversified, it has not made considerable impact on the development of the human capital. They submitted that the existing investment model of pension funds may not support the actualisation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations in this regard. Ndum, et al. (2019) discovered a "significant positive relationship between pension fund assets, pension fund

contribution, pension fund investment and gross domestic product” and recommended adequate management of pension fund as a way of ensuring pension fund sustainability.

These divergent opinions and submissions of the various studies further justify the need to understand the relationship between pension fund investment strategies and pension fund sustainability.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Harry Markowitz’s Portfolio Selection Theory. It came to light in 1952 and was published in the Journal of Finance. It was proposed to help investment decision strategy used by venture capitalists to make the most of gross earnings within a sustainable risk range. The theory was predicated on several assumptions: investors are rational with predictable behaviour; two type of assets exist with either low or high returns; the market is certain to go in a particular direction in an organized manner; diversification is the only way investment risk can be minimized; investors have open access to changes in market information and can make informed decisions; investors expected returns forecast are based on historical data and that risk measurement assets returns is either by variance or standard deviation (Markowitz, 1952). On the other hand, the theory has been criticised for too much reliance on historic data, extraneous assumptions that are often not real and the use of mean-variance as a replacement for potential risk (Wang, 2023).

The connection between the theory and the contributory pension fund investment strategies is that it is predicated on the assumptions of the theory. The asset type outlined in the Act is generally tailored to sustainable investment outlays. The deliberate effort to ensure a huge amount of the pension fund are invested in Federal and State government guaranteed assets as

well as real estate properties are attempted to align with the proposition advanced by the portfolio selection theory which is based on historical data of investors and market accessibility by pension stakeholders, practitioners and policy makers. The pension fund investments are diversified across some portfolios, which is another thrust of the theory. The National Pension Commission, through the Pension Fund Custodians and Pension Fund Administrators, has ensured investment strategies that are tailored towards pension asset security with adequate return on investment.

Methodology

The study engaged primary data through the use of a structured questionnaire and cross-sectional survey research design method and data was obtained from active and retired staff of the University of Teaching Hospital (UBTH), Benin City, Edo State. The population investigated was the active (3885) and retired staff (783) tallying 4668 from 2010 to 2022 both of the University of Benin Teaching Hospital who were beneficiaries of the contributory pension arrangement notwithstanding their cadre (Account Department UBTH, July 2023). A sample size of 400 was used instead of 368 arrived at in order to raise the spread and distribution. The sample size was obtained using the formula: $n = N/1+Ne^2$ (Yamane, 1981); where N is the population size, n is the sample size and e is the chance allowed for error or the level of significance and the reliability test was 0.831 using Cronbach Alpha technique for the questionnaire which were administered as the research instrument for data collection. The questionnaire contained a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 to 5 points. Data analysis was carried out using descriptive statistics, while linear regression analysis was used to examine the hypothesis of the study at a 5% significance level.

Data Presentation/Analysis

Regression Output for Pension Fund Investment Strategy on Pension Fund Sustainability

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.929 ^a	.863	.817	4.637		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Pension Fund Investment Strategy						
ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	405.482	1	398.544	18.855	.023 ^a
	Residual	64.518	399	17.453		
	Total	470.000	400			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Pension Fund Investment Strategy						
b. Dependent Variable: Pension Fund Sustainability						
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.140	4.813		.237	.828
	Pension Fund Investment Strategy	1.943	.217	.929	4.342	.023
a. Dependent Variable: Pension Fund Sustainability						

Source: Researchers Computation (2025)

From table above, it shows that the significant value (p-value) of the independent variable Pension Fund Investment Strategy is 0.023, which is less than 0.05. This indicates that there is a significant relationship between pension fund investment strategies and pension fund sustainability.

Discussion of Findings

The results obtained from the model data show that the R value is 0.924, which indicates that pension fund sustainability has a strong correlation with the pension fund investment strategy at [page 387](#)

92.4%. Also, the R^2 is 0.863, which indicates that 86.3% of pension fund sustainability was explained by pension fund investment strategy. The analysis shows that respondents agree that the nature of the contributory pension scheme investment strategies in the Pension Reform Act (2014) can ensure its sustenance. This position is endorsed in the work of Ijeoma et al. (2015), when their finding revealed significant evidence that pension investment strategies in existence can ensure the sustainability of the contributory pension scheme in Nigeria. Nwawolo et al. (2019) also supported the findings as their study revealed that contributors' decision-making on pension fund investment exerted a significant positive effect on retirees' standard of living.

Conclusion

The study based on empirical analysis believes that the introduction of pension fund investment strategies portrays a significant shift in pension administration in Nigeria. The beneficiaries at the University of Benin Teaching Hospital have a favourable and positive perception of the contributory pension fund investment strategies. There are indications that participants are optimistic that the scheme will make available pension entitlement upon retirement. There is evidence that the nature of investment strategies have contributed immensely to the sustained and continued successes of the pension scheme.

Recommendations

1. The National Pension Commission should maintain and reinforce its current successes in the contributory pension regime.
2. There should be continuous review and upgrade of pension fund investment strategies in line with international best practices.
3. There should be an alignment between pension fund investment strategies and the changing environment to preserve the culture of sustainability of the scheme.

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